

ExVivoMicroTest: Ex-Vivo Testing of Microservices

Online Appendix

Luca Gazzola¹, Maayan Goldstein², Leonardo Mariani¹, Marco Mobilio¹, Itai Segall³,
Alessandro Tundo¹, and Luca Ussi¹

¹Department of Informatics Systems and Communication (DISCo), University of
Milano-Bicocca, Milan Italy

²Nokia Bell Labs, Israel

³Nokia Bell Labs, United States of America

This is the online appendix of the paper Luca Gazzola, Maayan Goldstein, Leonardo Mariani, Marco Mobilio, Itai Segall, Alessandro Tundo and Luca Ussi. “ExVivoMicroTest: Ex-Vivo Testing of Microservices.” *Journal of Software: Evolution and Process (Special Issue: Automation of Software Test and Test Code Quality)*. (Accepted on 03/2022).

1 Covered Sequences

Figure 1: Statistics service: covered sequences.

Figure 2: Notification service: covered sequences.

Figure 3: Account service: covered sequences.

Figure 4: ts_consign_price service: covered sequences.

Figure 5: `ts_contacts` service: covered sequences.

Figure 6: `ts_food_map` service: covered sequences.

2 Traced Events

Figure 7: Statistics service: traced events.

Figure 8: Notification service: traced events.

Figure 9: Account service: traced events.

Figure 10: ts_consignment_price service: traced events.

Figure 11: `ts_contacts` service: traced events.

Figure 12: `ts_food_map` service: traced events.